

Objective 1.3 – Life Cycle assessment of Scottish vertical farming systems

Deliverable D1.3.1: Exploring the Scottish Context for the Project B1-6 Monitoring the environmental impact of controlled environment agriculture

21/02/2024

Summary

As the global population is set to increase to over 9 billion by 2050, there is increasing pressure on our global food production system. Furthermore, the issue of climate change threatens our food security, with food production itself one of the major contributors to global anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Controlled environment agriculture offers an alternative to traditional farming methods that is independent of climate and offers high quality produce. Vertical farming in particular, allows for food production in urban locations, while also removing the issue of seasonality and allowing for consistency in production.

This report compares the carbon footprints (CFs) found in literature for traditional farming methods against those of vertical farm (VF) produce, using seasonal leafy greens as an example crop. Though ranges were found in each of the possible production methods explored, VF showed the greatest range, showing both the highest and the lowest CF figures (37.19 - 0.16 kg CO₂ e per kg of produce) identified. While on average it had the highest CF (5.92 kg CO₂ e) and UK open field agriculture the lowest (0.46 kg CO₂ e), followed by Spanish open field agriculture (0.57 kgCO₂ e), the extremes in the range showed the importance of electricity production method in calculating a CF.

Scottish specific electricity mixes were modelled to explore the effect of regional grid variations on CF. A general decrease in CF was found as the Scottish grid transitioned towards fully renewable electricity use. In contrast, the modelled UK 2022 electricity grid mix showed one of the highest footprints explored by the study, surpassed only by the generic Great Britain mix supplied by the Ecoinvent database. This highlighted the importance of using up to date, region specific data when calculating CFs, particularly those with high contributions from electricity. Though it could not fully be extrapolated out from this data to estimate a single figure CF for Scottish VF produce, it does highlight the potential for it to be comparable or even environmentally preferable to other existing traditional production methods.

Key Messages

- Literature shows vertical farm produce to have the greatest range in carbon footprint when compared to open field agriculture in both Spain and the UK, and UK based greenhouses. This includes both the highest and lowest recorded CF in the study.
- This high variability can be attributed to differing methodological choices, as well as the type of electricity production and grid mix used.
- With the current grid mix in Scotland (as of 2022), there is the potential for Scottish vertical farms to create produce with a CF on par with that of open field agriculture.

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D1.3.1: Exploring the Scottish Context

Introduction

The purpose of this interim report (**Deliverable 1.3.1**) is to explore the understanding in literature of carbon footprints (CFs) for existing food production pathways within a Scottish context and comparing them to vertical farmed produce using seasonal leafy greens as an example crop. Further exploration was undertaken regarding hypothetical Scottish based vertical farms (VFs) and the significance of regional electricity grids on CF modelling.

Objective 1.3 as a whole, aims to develop baseline figures for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with VFs based in Scotland. This work is intended to take into consideration regional variability, and varying system boundaries. Case studies will be identified and undertaken to allow for the collection of real industry data to inform models and develop region specific ranges.

As a broader objective, the research summarised in this report is to act as a foundation for subsequent deliverables for this objective (**D1.3.2 and D1.3.3**) and ultimately inform the later **Objective 1.7**.

Background

There is increasing demand to produce food on a global scale as the population continues to rise, set to increase over 9 billion by 2050. An estimated 56-100% increase in food production is required to meet this rising demand for nutrition (McKenzie and Williams, 2015). The ability to achieve this is threatened by the changing climate (Seneviratne *et al.*, 2012; Church *et al.*, 2013; Chiang *et al.*, 2021), though food production itself has also been identified as one of the major global contributors towards anthropogenic GHG emissions. Food production is estimated to be responsible for 21-37% of overall GHG emissions worldwide (IPCC, 2019). In Scotland alone, agricultural GHG emissions were calculated at 7.6 MT CO₂ e (Lampkin *et al.*, 2019). It has been estimated that if business as usual is to continue with no changes to address food production emissions, the required increases could cause a 40% rise in GHG emissions (IPCC, 2019). As a result, there is mounting pressure to develop sustainable pathways for food production that will allow both the ability to increase food production to meet demand, and not further exacerbate the issue of climate change. In addition, Scotland possesses not only a colder and more variable climate than is typically found in other parts of the UK, but also has limited suitable arable land (The James Hutton Institute, 2022b, a). This restricts its

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ability to reliably produce and increase food production. Complications in import and export of food post Brexit and the COVID 19 pandemic (Freeman *et al.*, 2022), and agricultural labour shortages (Environment Food and Rural Affairs Committee, 2022) also highlight a need to reconsider current food production methods to ensure national food security.

Controlled system agriculture (CEA) is a logical contender for reliable food production which removes the variables of environment and climate as well as the constraints of limited agricultural space. It allows the producer to have complete control over inputs such as light, heat, water and nutrients. This permits the use of optimal settings during crop growth to allow for consistent results and increased yield, potentially as high as 10-100 times greater than open field agricultural systems (Engler and Krarti, 2021). There are many forms of CEA including polytunnels, glasshouses and the more modern concept of VFs. VF is a technique that allows for reducing the required land footprint in food production by adding in a vertical element with multiple levels for growing (Dano, 2018). As it exists in a fully controlled environment, it is generally accepted that it eliminates the requirement for pesticides, herbicides and soil based fertilisers (Despommier, 2010). In addition it can improve nutrient use and reduce water use by up to 50% and 95% respectively (Avgoustaki and Xydis, 2020). VF offers the potential to make use of unused buildings in rural and in urban areas, allowing for reliable production of crops in non-traditional settings. The VF industry is a fast growing area and estimated it will be worth approximately 33.02 billion USD by 2030 (Grand View Research, 2022).

Despite the many potential advantages of VF (Despommier, 2010; Avgoustaki and Xydis, 2020), there is less consistent information on its potential negatives. Given the global imperative towards climate smart food production, the environmental impacts of VF must be assessed before it can be considered as a potential sustainable production method for Scotland. In particular, possible environmental impacts must be explored within a Scotland specific context. This includes the effect of energy impacts, given Scotland's commitment to renewable energy (Scottish Government, 2020b) and net zero by 2045 (Scottish Government, 2019).

To begin to address this knowledge gap, this study sought to compare the CF of three existing procurement pathways for seasonal leafy greens consumed in Scotland (UK lettuce grown in open field agriculture, UK lettuce grown in glass houses, and Spanish lettuce grown in open field agriculture and transported over) with a hypothetical VF within Scotland. The following questions were proposed:

- 1) What are the relevant CF values found in literature for lettuce production in these three production pathways

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- 2) What CF ranges are found in literature for VF production of seasonal leafy greens?
- 3) How do these values compare with a modelled VF based in Scotland utilising Scotland specific energy mixes?

Preliminary results for this research were published in Sandison *et al.* (2023). Analysis has been expanded on since the publication, the results of which are summarised in this report.

Methods

Literature analysis

Literature on the topic of VF produce (primarily leafy greens) was reviewed and contrasted with literature on the production of lettuce in open field agriculture in the UK and in Spain, as well as greenhouse UK production. In the case of this report, VF was taken to mean intensive plant factories with artificial light, where all environmental aspects were fully controlled. Values for the CF (Global warming potential – GWP, measured in kg CO₂ e) for 1 kg of produce were extracted. Data regarding relative contributions towards the CF (e.g. electricity use, fertiliser use, etc) were also collected where possible to allow for hotspot analysis and for later modelling. A review was also undertaken to identify nutrient decline potential during transportation of goods.

Model analysis

The lack of transparency in many LCA papers did not allow for full modelling of a VF in Scotland at this stage, however there is a general consensus that electricity use dominates the CF of VF produce (Burgos and Stapel, 2018; Tennant, 2019; Blom *et al.*, 2022). For this reason, the decision was made to focus the interim model on the effects of electricity production on the resulting CF. Average electricity use figures were drawn from a study by Pennisi *et al.* (2019), which anecdotal evidence suggested to be in line with industry figures within Scotland. As energy use as a proxy for full CF has been demonstrated as suitable in other sectors (Parker, 2012; Sandison *et al.*, 2021), this was explored in the context of Scottish VF.

Models were run on SimaPro 9.2.0.2 using the (Guinée *et al.*, 2002) CML-IA methodology, and with background processes drawn from Ecoinvent 3.

Energy mix

Due to regional differences being noted in the electricity mixes between countries within the UK (Scottish Government, 2018; George, 2023; Scottish Government, 2023), and due to the range of CFs associated with different sources of electricity production (Table 1), specific energy mixes were made using up to date information for the UK (George, 2023) and Scotland (Scottish Government, 2023) using 2022 breakdown data. Historic data for Scotland (2017, 2019, 2020) was also explored (Scottish Government, 2018, 2020a, 2021). In addition, Norway's electricity mix data in 2022 (Statistics Norway, 2023; The Energy Institute, 2023) was used to allow contrast against a grid mix dominated by hydroelectricity rather than wind. In the cases of the UK mix and the Norwegian mix, it is assumed that generation pattern is the same as use pattern as no data could be found for preferential electricity use or exports as is documented in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2020a, 2023). The details of the electricity mixes created for each scenario can be found in Table 2.

Table 1: Carbon footprint and water footprint of 1 kW h electricity produced by different methods, adapted from Sandison *et al.* (2023)

Electricity production	Carbon footprint of 1 kWh (kg CO ₂ e)
Oil	1.28
Gas	0.513
Nuclear	0.0071
Wind onshore, >3MW turbine	0.0116
Wind offshore (1-3) MW turbine	0.0144
Hydro	0.00378

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Table 2: Percentage electricity mix for various countries and years, based on data from (Scottish Government, 2018, 2020a, 2021; George, 2023; Scottish Government, 2023; Statistics Norway, 2023; The Energy Institute, 2023)

	Gas	Oil	Nuclear	Biomass	Coal	Solar	Onshore wind	Offshore wind	Hydro	Other renewable	Other non-renewable	Imports	Energy Storage
Scotland 2017	8.6	2.8	35.6	0	0	0	34	0	11	8	0	0	0
Scotland 2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	56.5	9.4	15.8	8.4	9.9	0	0
Scotland 2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	60.2	10.7	19	8.6	0	0	0
Scotland 2022	0	0	0	0	0	0	67.1	15.1	13.88	7.93	0	0	0
Norway 2022	0.72	1.18	0	0	0	0	8.8	0	89.2	0	0	0	0
UK 2022	38.5	0	15.5	5.2	1.5	4.4	26.8	0	1.8	0	0	5.5	0.9

Renewable usage has increased in Scotland from 2017, rising from 53% to 90.1% in 2019, 98.6% in 2020, and finally reaching 100% by 2022 (see Table 2). It should be noted however that electricity use within Scotland and electricity production within Scotland is not the same with preferential use of renewable electricity within Scotland being shown, and non-renewables being exported (Scottish Government, 2021, 2023).

Where electricity generation was marked as 'other', the quantity was reallocated proportionally to suitable other existing electricity production types (with renewables allocated to renewable electricity production examples shown in the mix, and non-renewable allocated to non-renewable examples shown in the mix). Where 'storage' or 'imported' electricity was indicated, generic data for the regional mix was used from Ecoinvent for a proxy as no further information was available.

Transport and nutrient decline analysis

The effect of transport on nutrient decline was explored. Using data from literature, approximate distances for goods transport were identified (Milà i Canals *et al.*, 2008; Hospido *et al.*, 2009) and contrasted with an assumed 30km for local transport within a city. Assuming average speeds of 60mph over long distances (between city transports) and 30 over short distances (within city transport), as well as the necessity of an 8.5-hour overnight rest when transporting from Spain to the

UK, transport times were estimated. Using vitamin C as a proxy for nutrient decline (identified as a key nutrient in seasonal leafy greens), and data from Konstantopoulou *et al.* (2010), potential nutrient decline was modelled. This assumed a steady temperature of 5 degrees Celsius during transport. The effect of both closed and open packaging were explored for each transport scenario.

Results

Literature comparison

Ranges

The range of CF values found in literature for each of the production pathways are shown in Figure 1, with descriptive statistics given in Table 3. Both controlled system agriculture set ups (greenhouse in the UK and VF) show the largest ranges, with much smaller ranges seen in the open field agriculture pathways. Though a great deal of overlap is seen between all four pathways, average values find VF to have the highest impacts (5.92, or 3.08 kg CO₂ e per kg if extreme value is excluded) followed by greenhouse production (2.17 kg CO₂ e per kg), Spanish open field agriculture (0.56 kg CO₂ e per kg) and finally UK open field agriculture (0.46 kg CO₂ e per kg). VF is noted to have both the lowest value recorded (0.16 kg CO₂ e per kg) and the highest (37.19 kg CO₂ e per kg). The maximum figure has been excluded from Figure 1 as the value was so extreme that it obscured the details of the majority of the others within the image.

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Figure 1: Comparative carbon footprint ranges (kg CO₂ eq.) found in literature for producing 1 kg lettuce, where GH W, glasshouse grown in winter; GH S, glasshouse grown in summer; UK OF, open farm grown in the UK; S OF, open farm grown in Spain; VF, vertical farm grown. Whiskers on plot represent the range, X the average value, and dots representative of outliers. Based on data from literature (Milà i Canals *et al.*, 2008; Hospido *et al.*, 2009; Bartzas *et al.*, 2015; Benis and Ferrão, 2018; Burgos and Stapel, 2018; Nicholson *et al.*, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2020; Blom *et al.*, 2022; Baumont de Oliveira *et al.*, 2023; Martin *et al.*, 2023)

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of carbon footprint ranges in kg CO₂ eq. found in literature for producing 1 kg lettuce where GH W, glasshouse grown in winter; GH S, glasshouse grown in summer; UK OF, open farm grown in the UK; S FO, open farm grown in Spain; VF, vertical farm grown; VF+ Tennant (2019), VF scores including extreme value (Milà i Canals *et al.*, 2008; Hospido *et al.*, 2009; Bartzas *et al.*, 2015; Benis and Ferrão, 2018; Burgos and Stapel, 2018; Nicholson *et al.*, 2019; Tennant, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2020; Blom *et al.*, 2022; Baumont de Oliveira *et al.*, 2023; Martin *et al.*, 2023)

Descriptive stats	GH	SOF	UKOF	VF	VF+ Tennant (2019) value
Average	2.171429	0.574714	0.457143	3.082091	5.924264
Median	1.7	0.5	0.3	2.72	2.9685
Min	0.25	0.171	0.25	0.158	0.158
Max	4.75	1.375	1.2	7.75	37.18817
St. Dev	1.726475	0.3843	0.339643	2.393916	10.10669

Hotspot

Overall percentage contributions of each input were calculated to identify any major contributors or emission hotspots. Though UK open farm systems showed a fairly even spread of contributions, fertiliser use can be identified as having the biggest impact (27.6%), closely followed by general soil management (21.8%). In contrast, in the CF for Spanish open farm systems, transport featured most (42.5%), though fertiliser use (29.5%) was still second. In British greenhouses, heating dominated (81%), though in unheated (summer) greenhouses, cooling became the most dominant contributor (36.0%) followed by transport (23.5%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Analysis of relative contributions towards overall carbon footprint score for selected farming methods, where UK OF, open farm in the UK; S OF, open farm in Spain; GH, heated glasshouse; GH no heat, unheated glasshouse; VF, vertical farm. (Milà i Canals *et al.*, 2008; Hospido *et al.*, 2009)

Contribution figures in VF analysis showed a range to match their CF values. Though several were dominated by electricity use (Benis and Ferrão, 2018; Tennant, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2020; Blom *et al.*, 2022) others showed much lower values (Martin *et al.*, 2023; Parkes *et al.*, 2023) (Table 4). Nonetheless, electricity use does remain typically the largest contributor overall. An average contribution figure of 71% was calculated for electricity use and production. Figure 3 shows examples for full hotspot analysis for the two extreme values found in electricity contribution (Tennant, 2019; Martin *et al.*, 2023). In Tennant (2019), electricity accounts for 91% of the CF, with the next biggest contributor being substrate at 7% contribution. In contrast in Martin *et al.* (2023)

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though electricity remains the biggest contributor (39%), the next biggest contributors are packaging at 20% and transport at 17%.

Table 4: Percentage contribution of electricity production and use towards overall carbon footprint found in literature for 1kg of vertical farm produce

Study	% electricity contribution
Blom <i>et al.</i> (2022)	85%
Kikuchi <i>et al.</i> (2018)	75%
Martin <i>et al.</i> (2023)	39%
Tennant (2019)	91%
Benis and Ferrão (2018)	85%
Li <i>et al.</i> (2020)	90%
Parkes <i>et al.</i> (2023)	35%
Average	71%

Figure 3: Analysis of relative contributions towards overall carbon footprint score for two examples of vertical farms found in literature (Tennant, 2019; Martin *et al.*, 2023)

Modelled results

Models were run to explore the effect of different electricity mixes on CF. This was run for 1 kWh and for the average electricity use per kg of produce taken from Pennisi *et al.* (2019). This was then extrapolated out to explore the full CF if assuming that electricity represents 91% of the total (Tennant, 2019), 35% (Parkes *et al.*, 2023) and the average of 71% (Table 5). It was found that the default value for Great Britain from Ecoinvent provided the highest CF (ranging from 19.3-7.4 kg CO₂ e per kg), though this was closely followed by the UK 2022 value (15.7-6.1 kg CO₂ e per kg). Both are notably higher than the next highest value (Scotland 2017, 6.3-2.4 kg CO₂ e per kg). A general decrease in CF is seen in the Scottish data from 2017-2022 as renewable use increases towards 100%. The Norwegian 2022 mix was found to have the lowest ranges (0.3-0.8 kg CO₂ e per kg) though this was close to Scotland 2022 figures (0.39-1.00 kg CO₂ e per kg). The differences were seen to be from the increased use of hydropower over wind power (Table 1).

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Table 5: Comparison table of carbon footprints for selected electricity mixes for 1kWh, the average kWh requirement for producing 1 kg of produce (20.12 kWh as per Pennisi *et al.*, 2019), and the full carbon footprint for 1kg of produce if assuming electricity represents 35% of the overall CF (Parkes *et al.*, 2023), the average percent contribution found in literature (71% - this study), and 91% (Tennant, 2019)

	1 kWh	20.12 kWh	If 35%	If 71%	If 91%
GBH Ecoinvent (HV)	0.0930	6.740	19.257	9.493	7.407
UK 2022	0.0761	5.510	15.743	7.761	6.055
Scotland 2017	0.0254	2.220	6.343	3.127	2.440
Scotland 2019	0.0090	1.490	4.257	2.099	1.637
Scotland 2020	0.0060	0.420	1.200	0.592	0.462
Scotland 2022	0.0048	0.350	1.000	0.493	0.385
Norway 2022	0.0038	0.270	0.771	0.380	0.297

Transport and nutrient decline

Using data from literature, transport distances for produce from each production pathway were estimated. An estimation of 2600km was used for produce travelling from Spain to the UK and 200km for transport from farm to point of sale within the UK for open field produce (Milà i Canals *et al.*, 2008; Hospido *et al.*, 2009). No suitable data assumptions were identified for transport distance for VF. Instead, a general estimation of 30km was assumed for within city transport. The details of assumptions made can be found in Table 6.

Using the data from Table 6, estimations of nutrient loss were made (Table 7). Both open and closed packaging were explored at different concentrations of applied nitrogen as per Sandison *et al.* (2023). A greater nutrient decline was identified in produce coming from Spain (approximately 5% for open packaging and 2.5% for closed). This was higher than other pathways, with the next highest being open packaging from UK open field agriculture (0.33%).

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Table 6: Estimated transport distance and time for lettuce produced under select farming methods for onward sale in Scotland as per Sandison *et al.* (2023)

	UK OF	UK GH	Scottish VF	SOF
Transport distance (km)	200	200	30	2600
Transport time	2h 4min	2h 4min	37 min	35h 5min
Assumptions	Assuming an average of 60mph	Assuming an average of 60mph	Assuming an average of 30mph	Assuming an average of 60 mph. inclusive of 8.5h rest period rather than continual driving

Table 7: Calculated loss of vitamin C in seasonal leafy greens in open and closed packaging, based on expected transport times for lettuce production pathways for Scotland at 5 degrees centigrade as per Sandison *et al.* (2023)

% loss of vitamin C during transport								
N concentration applied (mg NL-1)		20	80	140	200	260	Average % loss	Average Vit C decline from harvest (mg 10-1 g.f.w)
UK produce	Closed packaging	0.01	0.05	0.15	0.2	0.2	0.12	0.15
	Open packaging	0.36	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.22	0.27	0.33
Vertical farm produce	Closed packaging	0	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.05
	Open packaging	0.11	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.1
Spanish produce	Closed packaging	0.15	0.88	2.48	3.65	3.36	2.1	2.54
	Open packaging	5.99	4.53	4.39	4.39	3.65	4.59	5.53

Discussion

Literature review

The range found in literature for CFs in VFs showed both the highest (Tennant, 2019) and the lowest (Burgos and Stapel, 2018) values over all the production pathways explored. One explanation for this is that the VF industry is still relatively young (Van Gerrewey *et al.*, 2021), with technological developments and optimal methodological choices still being explored. Literature has highlighted correlations between growth rate and several factors including rate of harvest, ratio of red/blue spectral components in the lighting (Pennisi *et al.*, 2019) nutrient solution concentration (Foster, 2018; Hosseini *et al.*, 2021) as well as distance between lights to plants and photoperiod interval (Foster, 2018). With so many potentially influencing factors, it is hard to determine which have affected the overall CF in the case of each study. However, the hotspot analysis nonetheless identifies energy use as the most influential aspect in a VF, with even studies showing the lowest contribution by electricity (Martin *et al.*, 2023; Parkes *et al.*, 2023) still finding it to be the largest contributor to the overall impact.

Burgos and Stapel (2018) reported a range in their study of 5.74-0.16 kg CO₂ e) with the latter being the lowest recorded CF value for VF produce identified. This value was identified as from a 'improved VF', namely one that utilised renewable energy and that optimised energy use. The higher numbers recorded in the study were from typical VFs. This suggests that at least some of the range can be attributed to choice of electricity mix.

The high value seen in Tennant (2019) is likely due to the VF being studied still being in its development phase rather than at commercial launch. During this phase, optimisation settings are explored and as such may not be identified or implemented during the time of the study. This highlights the potential importance of methodological decisions on an environmental front as well as an economic one.

Modelled results

The modelled results highlight the importance of region-specific electricity mixes. Reliance on the generic Great Britain mix from Ecoinvent offers the highest possible results, though use of UK 2022 mix has the second biggest impact. While there is a notable difference between the two (approximately 20%), the differences between the UK and the Scottish mixes are larger still, with the lowest difference showing UK 2022 to be 67% higher than the Scottish 2017 mix, and 94% higher

than the Scotland 2022 mix. This is a substantial difference, and when run in a modelled scenario using figures from Pennisi *et al.* (2019) to represent production of 1kg of VF produce, this resulted in over 5kg of difference in CO₂ e. This would alter VF produce from having a CF roughly in line with the average figures found in the literature, but being substantially higher than other production pathways, as opposed to it potentially being a competitive production option. It is possible that there may be discrepancies in the modelled UK results in that the authors could not determine if the UK as a whole has shown any preferential export of energy, resulting in different production and use figures as is found in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2021, 2023), however it seems unlikely that if this were the case, preferential figures regarding emissions and renewable targets would not be easier found. The Norwegian 2022 mix shows a more favourable footprint to the Scottish one (0.0038 kg CO₂ e per kWh, as opposed to 0.0048 for Scotland 2022). This along with differences between the Scottish mix over the years stresses both that up-to-date energy production information is key, as well as regional variation being important when exploring models that rely on electricity as a major component. While there is a clear correlation between increasing use of renewable electricity production and reducing CF, the differences in the Scottish 2022 and Norwegian 2022 mix highlight that choice of renewable production is also important, with hydroelectricity showing a lower CF per kWh than wind generated power (Table 1).

While the contribution analysis showed a variable importance of electricity production and use on a CF, it remained the largest sole contributor in the studies explored. This argues for it remaining as an important area to focus on when exploring reduction options. However, as its relative contribution varied markedly, then it is also important that research into Scottish based VFs continue. Industry data is required to explore both the contribution relevance in this region, but also the variation found between farms within Scotland to determine if variation is farm-farm, or if regional patterns can be identified.

While it is difficult to project any likely CFs for VF produce in a Scottish VF without exploring industry data, both for absolute electricity use, and for relative contribution to overall CF, this study has shown that utilising the current Scottish energy grid mix (2022) there is the potential to create produce from VFs on par with or lower than other production pathways. While the underlying assumptions would need to be tested in future work, this highlights Scottish VFs as having the potential to help towards meeting Scotland's net zero targets while increasing food production and ensuring national food security.

Transport and nutrient decline

Despite transport being over much greater differences in Spanish produce (Milà i Canals *et al.*, 2008; Hospido *et al.*, 2009) and highlighted as one of the larger contributors, Spanish produce still presented as one of the lowest impact production options in literature. It showed to be only marginally greater than UK open field produce, which is restricted by season. This would appear to argue that based on these results, the best options from a CF perspective for sourcing seasonal leafy greens are from open field agriculture in the UK in season, and from Spain when out of season. However, closer exploration into the ranges seen, show this is entirely dependent on case-by-case situations, as VF has the potential to offer a comparable or lower option as well as one much higher (Tables 3 and 5). Given the link with electricity, and the current Scottish electricity mix, this suggests that Scottish VF grown produce does have the ability to meet the goal of low GHG emission if an optimised set up is utilised. It should also be noted, that because of the importance of electricity use in the end figure of CF for heated greenhouses, that other CEA options might also show similarly low CFs within Scotland.

Nutrient decline is a consideration in sourcing produce as well. Though not high level, the 2.5-5.5% estimated decline in vitamin C found in Spanish produce is nonetheless higher than other production and transport options. This could prove an issue if there were any delays in transport, effecting vegetable lifespan on the outlet shelves and post purchase. Though vitamin C was used to represent key nutrients in this study, it should be noted that some other nutrients (carotenoids, vitamins K and A, folate, etc) are more easily affected and may show an increased rate of decline in transport, particularly if not kept fully hydrated. Other studies have found that prolonged transport and/or storage can have negative effects on the attractiveness to the customer, as well as shelf life and mineral loss (Managa *et al.*, 2018). Though the lowered nutrient loss is found in closed packaging (2.5% decline), the added packaging material required for this will also come with its own CF implications.

Next Steps

Engagement with the VF industry is already underway, allowing for real VF data to be obtained for farms within the UK and further abroad. This will allow for full LCA models to be built for UK and Scottish based farms. As well as offering individual insights, this will also potentially allow for a range to be established for inputs within Scotland, allowing for greater generalisations to then be drawn

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with regards to relative importance of electricity and other aspects such as substrate. Further refinement will be undertaken for the Scottish electricity mix and comparison with other global electricity grids and default database values will be explored. Investigation will also be undertaken to non-grid electricity options such as dedicated solar panels, gas generators and localised wind turbines. The effects of optimisation and further methodological choices (e.g. substrate choice) will also be explored later in the project.

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